

The Waqf on Islamic media institutions a comparative study

Dr.Mohyi Aldin Yaqob Abu Alhoul
Ajloun University

ABSTRACT

The Islamic WAQF is one of the most prominent experiences on the human level, which is unique in its ability to address deficiencies in the economic and social structure, and to transfer thought to a stage of developmental interaction, and there is no doubt that the Islamic civilization has been able to use this product efficiently and effectively over the years and ages, until it lasted Aspects of life. With fluctuations and disparities related to the general condition of the Islamic nation, this research comes to open the door wide in one of the most important contemporary applications of Islamic media institutions. To achieve this, I have used the inductive approach and the deductive analytical method, exerting the strength and energy in it, using the sayings and interviews of scholars, thinkers and specialists, studying and examining to her. The research produced results, the most important of which is the permissibility and legality of the WAQF on Islamic media, due to its importance and ability to develop Islamic media.

Key words: Waqf, Media, Islamic Media, Media, Development.

1 Introduction

The Islamic WAQF has been an amazing and rapid ability to advance the Islamic nation scientifically and culturally, which has contributed to the steadfastness of the Islamic identity with all the occupation, colonialism and displacement it has been subjected to.

The WAQF, as an economic institution that belongs to Muslims, is of great importance as it is the main source for building and caring for the most important Islamic educational institutions starting from the mosques from which the Qur'anic writings and schools branched off, then it becomes an independent financial institution that performs economic, social and cultural public services, and sometimes and strategically, and covers a wide area Social, educational, health and environmental interests, infrastructure services and others.

However, the serious challenges that the Islamic nation has been exposed to have affected its pillars, which was reflected in the form of disturbance in the contemporary WAQF work that took it away from the purpose of its legislation as one of the most important methods of rebuilding the land. The internal challenge related to legislation and guidance is the most prominent and important challenge around which a lot of controversy and discussion arose, which motivated the sincere people to document the achievements and devise realistic solutions in an attempt to invest this Islamic product and employ it in our contemporary life It is better than importing Western experiences that are deficient in dealing with the financial crises the world is experiencing, and in order to achieve the interest of mankind at all times and places. God has left the door of ijihad in the WAQF wide open Islam's interest in the Islamic WAQF stems from its consideration of it as a continuous source of goodness that does not benefit from benefit, but goes beyond the world's life, WAQFs have participated in establishing mosques and Islamic centers, establishing houses of knowledge, hospitals, and

Ligands. They have also had a prominent role in supporting Islamic jihad, and Muslims have raced over the years to endow their property for various charitable causes.

The media comes with the influence and power it possesses, as one of the most important features of this era, which has developed and diversified its methods and means, which made it a highly influential force. To broad sectors of societies of all kinds and diversity, as it does its work in the minds and souls of people, and is reflected in their decisions and actions, and then affects their attitudes and stances that they take on many issues.

There is no doubt that the contemporary Islamic media is one of the jihadist means available these days, as it covers two great aspects of the renaissance of the nation and society, by communicating and correctly communicating the religion to the West, and standing in the face of accusations directed against Islam and Muslims, and confronting them with this method. It is one of the most successful and fastest solutions in communicating the goal, and it is the most interactive and attractive way to attract the West towards it. It also contributes to addressing the nation's masses and protecting them from strange Western appearances, and it is one of the biggest things that we can use the contemporary media to treat, protect and deliver its material.

2The Concept Of A Waqf In Language And Legitimacy

In the language, WAQF comes with multiple meanings, including imprisonment and prohibition of acting. It is said: it stood like this: that is to hold it, and forbade it, and it is used as a metaphor in the sense of being informed or briefing and restricting it. Then it became known that the word WAQF was applied to the arrested, and it expresses the WAQF by imprisonment, and it is said in Morocco: Minister of Habas (Al-Razi, vol. 1, p. 305, Ibn Manzur, vol.9, p. 362). (And stop themThey are to be questioned) (As-Saffat: 24).

As for the terminology of the jurists, Al-Sarkhasi defined it by saying: "Imprisonment from ownership by others . (Al-Sarkhasi, vol.12. P27) The author of al-Hidayah mentioned the definition of the WAQF according to Abu Hanifa and among the two companions by saying: "It is according to Abu Hanifa: the custody of the eye on the king of the WAQF. Giving the benefit of a benefit, and according to the Malikis: giving the benefit of something while it is in existence, it is necessary for it to remain in the property of the one who gives it, even if it is in recognition of it (Ibn Arafa, 1993, vol. 2, p539).

Al-Shafi'iism: Withholding money that can be used, while remaining in its eye, by cutting off the disposition of his neck on a permissible and existing side "(El-Sherbiny, 1415 AH, Part 2, p360)

Hanbali: confinement of the owner, the absolute disposition, of his usufruct money, while remaining in his eyes, by cutting off the behavior of the stand and others in his neck, to spend his proceeds to a point of righteousness, and to receive the benefit. To draw closer to Allah "(Al-Bahooti, vol. 4, p. 240).

Every person who has an opinion has narrative and mental evidence on which it is based that is not desirable to introduce in this regard (Shalabi, pp. 309-312.).

And the reciter of the phrase of the jurists and the diligent in this field, he notes that the general orientation they have and through in-depth analysis of the evidence of each team, taking into account the developments of our time, is to say that the WAQF is necessary. And that the eye is suspended for God Almighty. (Al-Qasimi, p8.) The WAQF is forever according to the majority of jurists. It cannot be determined with time, so it is only suitable for what is suitable for perpetuation and its continued existence within the determinants of which they differed in detail.

Legitimacy of WAQF: There is no mention in the Noble Qur'an of WAQF in its idiomatic sense, but in that it is charity and the donation of the products of WAQF in the object of good. And the path of goodness is considered to be included in the verses that Dawah for goodness and charity, and spending for the sake of God, the Almighty said(O you who believe! Spend of the good things you have earned, and of what We have produced for you from the earth. And do not pick the inferior things to give away, when you yourselves would not receive it, except with closed eyes. And know that Allah is Self-Sufficient, Praiseworthy.) (Surah Albaqarah Verse 267)•And the Almighty saying) (Whatever good you forward for yourselves, you will find it with Allah) (Surat Al-Baqarah Verse (110). And General rebuked the Almighty) (You will never attain virtuous conduct until you give from what you love. Whatever you give away, Allah knows about it.)((Surat Al-Imran Verse 92).

There are a large number of hadiths indicating a general or private indication of the legitimacy of the WAQF in word or deed.

3 Sections And Forms Of WAQF In General

The WAQF is divided as the WAQF is: charitable WAQF, atomic WAQF, and joint WAQF.

The WAQF is divided into: the WAQF of the real estate, the WAQF of the movable property, the WAQF of cash, the WAQF of benefits, and the suspension of rights.

It is divided according to time into: a permanent WAQF, and temporary suspension with time. It is divided into consideration of legality: a valid WAQF and an invalid

3 Islamic Media

Media in language: the media is a language that is derived from the past tense "know" and its present tense "inform" and its source is information. "And the most knowledgeable comes from knowledge and it is a perception of something as it is, and I informed and taught it in the first place, except that the media is concerned with what was quick news and education is concerned with what is to be repeated And the multiplication of it until it has an effect on the same teacher (Ibn Manzur, vol. 12, p. 416)

Definition of media in terminology: As for the definition of media in terminology, the follower of the efforts of media professionals and researchers in this field is aware of the extent of their suffering in controlling an inclusive definition of media, and with their convergence, their definitions cannot be matched, and this is a natural matter resulting from the modernity of this science, and on this, examples must be given These definitions are attributed to their owners (Hamza, 1965, p. 23), and we mention of them:

The definition of the German scientist Autogrou, which is appreciated by the majority of media scholars: "It is the objective expression of the mentality, spirit, tendencies and trends of the masses at the same time (Abd al-Latif 1978, p. 76) in the sense that the media must be distinguished by honesty, away from whims and tendencies, away from prejudice, It is based on honest experience, consistent with the nature of the audience it addresses.

A group of scholars went on to criticize the definition of Autogrou by saying that its definition is an objective expression, meaning that it is not a self-expression on the part of the journalist, broadcaster, or movie or television man, but rather it is a purely objective expression in the sense that it is based on facts, figures and statistics or on them together if necessary. (Al-Araji 1980, p9.)

Definition of Islamic media: Islamic media has been defined by several definitions, including:

1- (It is a deliberate, planned, continuous and sincere technical artistic effort by a contact person, whether a body, a group, or an individual who has a broad and in-depth background in the subject of the message he addresses and aims to contact the general public, its qualitative bodies and individuals, with all the capabilities of the media and conviction with the aim of forming a correct public opinion that is aware Religious facts, which he perceives and is influenced by them in his beliefs, worship, and dealings.) (Kahil 1998, p29)

2-(It is the use of an Islamic approach in an artistic media style, carried out by learned Muslims who work with their religion, who understand the nature of media and its

modern means, and its diverse audiences, using these advanced means to spread short ideas, modern news, moral values, principles and ideals, for Muslims and non-Muslims, at all times And in every place, and within the framework of complete objectivity, with the aim of guidance, awareness and guidance, to have the required effect, and to know the extent of the influence first-hand) (Al-Fityani 1987, p.29)

Islamic media does not differ in style and content from contemporary media, but it is based on Islamic law with a special color in substance, content and form, and it must express the values of Islamic societies. The media process is launched to define the cultural, economic, and educational goals of the Islamic community, and even entertainment and enjoyment in accordance with the rules and values of Islam through truthful news. The evidence for this in the Islamic strength is clear. From the very first moment, all available media tools have been used to inform the Islamic religion in its spiritual and material parts, which is consistent with the formation and needs of man. Allah says:

(And among His signs is that He created for you spouses from among yourselves, so that you may find tranquility in them; and He planted between you love and compassion. In this are signs for people who think) (Surah Al-Rum Verse 21) And also the Almighty saying) : (He who perfected everything He created; and originated the creation of the human being from clay). (Surah Al-Sajdah Verse 7).

The best blessing that God bestowed upon us is the blessing of guidance to Islam, for it is all good. We proceed in this from our faith as Muslims, and it is the first thing that we must do. God imposes it on us to inform it and make it a lived reality away from ignorance. And we confront the haters, and this is what the Ummah has pursued throughout its history, following that of the Prophet.

This will only come from exerting effort in spreading the sciences of Islam and its correct ideas, an explanation of what is hidden and employment in the lives of people, and an explanation of the ambiguous and the removal of illusions, so the people of Islam must push ignorance, likeness and delusion so that the breasts are filled with truth and moderation.

Dawah to God is a legal obligation, as the community's consensus on that was reported through the words of the commentators, commentaries, the Qur'an, the Sunnah, and evidence for its obligation, and many of them we mention (Ibn Taymiyyah, 15, p. 157):

First: God Almighty said:

And let there be among you a community dawah to virtue, and advocating righteousness, and deterring from evil. These are the successful. (Surat Al Imran, Verse 14),The sign of the verse is clear on the necessity of dawah, so the letter lam comes in saying "Let it be" categorical in that, and it came "from you," indicating the necessity of sufficiency. The ummah is commanded to find someone from her who performs this duty. An individual duty, just as the obligation is waived for the rest, otherwise the entire ummah will be guilty of sin

And this is in terms of reviving the obligation and continuing to perform it, but when the Muslim sees an evil that his companions speak out loudly, then the Messenger of God has indicated the duty to the Muslim in this case, and he said: (Whoever among you sees an evil, then let him change it with his hand, and if he is unable, with his tongue, then he cannot. In his heart, that weakened the faith) (Muslim No. 49.)

That is why this great and comprehensive vocation was necessary from strong preachers, a stern and patient gift who was commensurate with its greatness and comprehensiveness, able to extend the rays of its light in the souls, minds and consciences of people, after their needs shone with them and their lives were illuminated by them.

Evidence from the Qur'an and Sunnah indicates the necessity of dawah to God Almighty and that it is one of the obligatory duties) :invite to your Lord's Way with wisdom and good advice, and debate with them in the most dignified manner. Your Lord is aware of those who stray from His path, and He is aware of those who are guided) (Surah Al-Nahl Verse 125)

And the Almighty said: (Say, "This is my way: I invite to Allah, based on clear knowledge, and whoever follows me. Glory be to Allah, and I am not of the associators) (Surah Yusef verse 108)

So God demonstrates that the followers of the Messenger are the callers to God, and they are the people of insights and the duty as it is known is to follow him and follow his path, may God bless him and grant him peace, as the Almighty said: (You have in the Messenger of Allah an excellent example, for those who hope for Allah and the Last Day and remember Allah much.)(Surat Al-Ahzab verse 21)

The scholars have stated that dawah to the Almighty is an obligation that is sufficient for the countries in which the preachers make the Dawah. Because every country and every region needs the continuity of the Dawah, which is expressed in our time through the Islamic media.

4 Waqf for Islamic Media

By tracing the WAQF system in the Islamic system throughout history, it shows us its many positives and great capabilities in the areas of easing the burdens of the Islamic community and contributing to its service, by meeting its needs and requirements. The WAQF strengthens and supports the community's bonds, and taking care of it in this age is an urgent humanitarian and legal necessity, for a renewed need. each period.

The Qur'anic verses and hadiths that urge spending for the sake of God in general have multiplied, and Sharia has defined several forms of this spending, including zakat and voluntary alms in general, including current alms that are based on the WAQF, so the objectives of the WAQF in Islam, as it is known, are not limited to Building mosques or helping the poor with money. Rather, it goes beyond that to provide public benefit and achieve the interests of all Muslims, in all fields, so that the Islamic WAQFs included non-Muslims, and there is no doubt that the media institution is one of those public benefits and interests that aim to build the structure of this society. And this can only be done with his support and financially financed so

that he can achieve the intended and desired, as WAQFs are one of these important and alternative means that help build the media institution.

The WAQF has a great and great role in achieving the great interests of Islamic societies, on top of which is the role in social, economic, cultural and political life, as the fulfillment of these roles in the Islamic society makes it on the ladder of civilized and human progress and elevates it forward.

Among the areas that the WAQF achieves is building the cultural aspect in the Islamic community and nation, and one of these areas is building visual media institutions, and there is no doubt that building such institutions is necessary, especially if they achieve the desired and desired goals, and that they represent a legitimate alternative to contemporary Islamic media. It also achieves some aspects of the political aspect, being another type of

Types of jihad, the jihad of the pen and the tongue, in defending the society's thorn by confronting similarities and accusations.

It has been decided in the past that the legal ruling to find an Islamic journalist is "WAJEB KFAYAH", which if some are based on its establishment and establishment, the demand for others will fall .In light of what we have noticed these days that this aspect has been overlooked by many, and states and institutions have failed about it, and ignored the extent of its countless positives and good deeds, and the extent of its service to the children of Muslims in finding their goals and desires, which dawah for finding ways and means that support this aspect, namely: Supporting media institutions financially, so that it can stand on its feet, facing the challenges and obstacles that prevent it from establishing it properly.It will meet the demand to contribute to building media institutions. (Al-Tamimi 1996, p 43).

And if it is decided that the Islamic media is nothing but a means for an intended purpose, namely, enjoining good and forbidding evil, giving advice, and a statement of duties and rights, it is necessary for us to spend on it various resources, and among these important resources are WAQFs, which, as we said, contribute to building scientific and cultural life. And there is no doubt that the Islamic media is one of the most prominent means that achieve and revive this life in the Islamic community, especially in providing educational, educational and religious programs to families, the young, the old, the youth, and institutions, each with what suits him and needs it,

and in light of this it is obligatory for Muslims, individuals and groups, to specialize some Their money is as WAQF for the sake of spending for the sake of God and for the purposes of good in general,

And that there are sponsors of these WAQFs, whether they are official or individual, that will develop the WAQFs and employ their proceeds in the service and support of the Islamic media, by supporting its channels and financing its programs and websites (Abu Qarn 2008, pp. 112-116)

5 Conclusion

With the end of the research, we can mention the most important results as follows:

- 1 The person familiar with the concept of Islamic media understands that it is a practical practice of the Islamic da'wah, in its many forms and means
- 2 The Islamic media faces serious financing challenges in the way of its hard work, which requires us to think of new means
- 3 The WAQF is one of the most important Islamic products that benefit society as a whole and can be used to finance purposeful Islamic media, in a way that guarantees it can play its role freely and efficiently, enabling it to fill the void occupied by traditional media.
- 4 The creation and empowerment of contemporary Islamic media is considered a discretionary duty, and this duty may rise to the concrete duty, especially for the legal specialists and media professionals.
- 5 It is permissible to spend some of the WAQF money on Islamic media, as a matter of advocacy, guidance and spreading knowledge, and there is no doubt that this is one of the aspects of goodness and righteousness that Islam has urged to activate and establish.

6 References

1. The holy quran
2. Prophetic hadith
3. Abu lil. Mahmud 'ahmadu. 1422h-22disambir . Aistithmar al'awqaf fi alfiqh al'iislamii . Aldawrat althaalithat eashra . Kuyt:majmae alfiqh al'iislamii .
4. Abuqirna, yusuf eali salim 2008, 'ahkamuh wadawabituh fi alfiqh al'iislamiu,rsalat majistir aljamieat al'urduniyati.
5. Al'aeraji, zuhayr 1980, alshakhsiat al'iislamiat muasasat 'iislamiyatun, altabeat al'uwlaa, dar altaeawun lilmatbueati, bayrut.
6. Al'arnawuwta. Muhamad 1323hi. Alwaqf fi aldawlat aleuthmania (majalat 'awqaf , aleadad : 3 , alsanat althaaniat , ramadan , 1423 h).
7. Albukhari. Muhamad bn 'iismaeil albukhariu aljuefiu1993.sahih bikhari. Dar abn kathiri.
8. Aldisuqiu.lilshaykh muhamad bin earfat aldisuqii1996. Hashiat aldisuqi ealaa alsharh alkabiri. Bayrut: dar alkutub aleilmiati.
9. Aleayni. Mahmud bin 'ahmad . 1980. Albinayat fi sharh alhidayati. Bayrut: dar alfikri.
10. Alfityani, taysir mahjub 1987, muqawimat rajul al'iislam al'iislamii.
11. Alhadadi. 'Ahmad bin eabd aleaziz 1422hi. Waqf alnuqud wastithmariha. Kabir mufatin bidayirat alshuwuwn al'iislamiat waleamal alkhayrii bidabi.
12. Alhasakafay. Eala' aldiyn 1979. Aldir almukhtar. Bayrut: dar alfikri.
13. Alhasani, khalifat babkur1999 . Astithmar mawarid al'awqaf 1420h nufimbir. Aldawrat althaaniat eashra . Mujmae alfiqh al'iislamii .almamlakat alearabiat almaghribiati.
14. Alhatabi. Muhamad bin eabd alrahman altarabulsi almaghribi. 1423hu. Mawahib aljalil lisharh mukhtasar khalil. Bayrut: dar ealam alkutub.
15. Alkbisi, muhamadu.1397h. 'Ahkam alwaqf fi alsharieat al'iislamiati. Baghdad : matbaeat al'iirshadi.
16. Alkharshi.muhamad bin eabdallah.1997. Hashiat alkhharshi. Bayrut: dar alkutub aleilmiati.
17. Almardawi. Eala' aldiyn eali sulayman1997. Al'iinsafu. Bayrut: dar alkutub aleilmiati.
18. Alsadlan, salih bin ghanima. 'Ahkam alwaqf walwasiat walfarq baynahima.dar bialnasiati.

19. Alsarkhisi. Muhamad bin 'abi sahla. 1406hi. Almabsuta. Bayrut: dar almaerifati.
20. Alshirbini. Muhamad alkhathib. Mughaniy almuhtaji. Bayrut: dar 'iihya' alturath alearabii.
21. Alshiyrazi. 'Ibrahim ealii 1379mi. Almuhadhibi. Bayrut: dar almaerifati.
22. Altamimi, alkhathibu1996: mashrueiat alwaqf watabieatuh wa'anwaeuhu, mushkilatih wahululi, bahath mirfaq fi kitab silsilat nadawat alhiwar bayn almuslimina, bieunwan 'ahamiyat al'awqaf alaslamiat fi ealam alyawmi, jameiat eumaal almatabie altaeawuniat, eamaan - al'urdunn.
23. Altarabulsi. Alshaykh 'iibrahim bin musaa . 1918. Al'iiseaf fi 'ahkam al'awqaf . Bayrut - lubnan :dar alraayid alearabii.
24. Alzarqa. Shaykh mustafaa. 1366ha. Ahkam alawaqafi. Dimashqa: matbaeat aljamieat alsuwriati.
25. Dunya . Shawqi 'ahmad 2001ma. Alwaqf alnaqdiu . Aldawrat althaalithat eashar . Alkuayti: mujmae alfiqh al'iislamii.
26. Eabd allatifi, hamzat 1978, al'iielam waldieayatu, altabeat althaaniatu, alqahirata, dar alfikr alearabii.
27. Ibn alhamami. Muhamad bin eabd alwahidi. Sharh fath alqidiri. Birut: dar alfikri.
28. Ibn 'ansa. Maliki. Almudawanati. Alqahirati: matbaeat alsaeadati.
29. Ibn eabidin, muhamad 'amin . 1486hi. Hashiat abn eabdin.qahirata: mustafaa alhalbi.
30. Ibn majahi. Muhamad bn yazid alquzwini. 1984. Sunan abn majah. Alrayad: sharikat altibaeat alearabiat alsueudiati.
31. Ibn manzurin1990m. Lisan alearbi. Bayrut: dar sadr.
32. Ibn qudamata. 'Ahmad muhamadu. 1981. Almughni. Alrayad: maktabat alriyad alhadithati.
33. Ibn taymiati. 'Ahmad eabd alhalim. Majmue fatawaa shaykh al'iislam abn taymiati. Bayrut: dar alearabiati.
34. Kahil 1998, al'usus aleilmiat waltatbiqiat lil'iielam al'iislamii, ealam alkutub.
35. Khalifa. 'Idris. 1999ma. Aistithmar mawarid al'awqaf . Aldawrat althaaniat eashra . Mujmae alfiqh al'iislamii . Almamlakat alearabiat almaghribi.
36. Khalifatu. Haji. Kashaf alzunun . Bimakat almukaramat :maktabat alfaysalia .

37. Majalat mujmae alfiqh al'iislami . 1408hi-1988m . Aldawrat alraabiea . Aleadad alraabie . Aljuz' althaalith . Munazamat almutamar al'iislami.
38. Quhfu, mundhir. 2000. Alwaqf al'iislami: tutawiruh 'iidaratuh watanmiatuha. Dimashqa: dar alfikri.
39. Quhfu. Mundhir.2000 . Alwaqf al'iislamiu. Dimashq . Suriatun: dar alfikri.